

Effect of planting time on SR incidence at Kaul, India.

Variety	Infected tillers (%)				Reduction in disease (%) over 18 Jul planting	
	18 Jul	3 Aug	18 Aug	Mean	3 Aug planting	8 Aug planting
Jaya	59	35	3	32	40	95
Jhona 349	19	80	25	61	-2	68
Pusa 33	66	62	5	44	6	92
Basmati 310	25	15	1	14	42	95
HAU 118-110	11	5	3	6	53	76
HAUK 2313-39	24	19	3	15	19	86
Mean	44	36	7			

CD at 5%

For comparison of means of 2 planting dates

4.52

For comparison of means of 2 varieties

2.14

For interaction (planting date × variety)

4.14

varieties except Jhona 349 was significantly less in the 3 Aug planting. This was attributed to lower temperatures (23°C) and relative humidity (69%) during susceptible stages (see table). *ℒ*

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Pest Control and Management INSECTS

Influence of plant density on oviposition by whorl maggot (RWM)

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We studied the influence of spacing of transplanted and wet seeded IR36 on the number of RWM *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino eggs laid per plant and the degree of RWM damage.

The experiment was in a split-plot design with planting methods as main plots and plant and seed density as subplots. In transplanted plots, hill spacings were 10 × 10, 20 × 20, and 40 × 40 cm. In wet seeded plots, seed rates were 160, 120, and 80 kg/ha. Three seedlings per hill were transplanted 15 d after sowing. Pregerminated seeds were sown in wet seeded plots on the same day. Plots were flooded 3 d after sowing

RWM damage and egg density as affected by plant density in transplanted and wet seeded IR36.^a IRRI, 1983 DS.

Plant density	Eggs (no.) at indicated days after transplanting or sowing						Damaged leaves (%) 23 DT/DS
	Per m ²			Per plant			
	8	18	28	8	18	28	
<i>Transplanted</i>							
Spacing							
10 × 10 cm	124 c	481 c	179 b	1.2 a	4.9 a	1.8 a	54 a
20 × 20 cm	319 b	192 b	135 b	12.8 b	7.7 b	5.4 a	65 ab
40 × 40 cm	183 a	139 a	70 a	29.3 c	22.1 c	112 b	15 b
<i>Wet seeded</i>							
Seed rate (kg/ha)							
160 kg/ha	189 c	223 b	110 b	0.39 a	0.41 a	0.23 a	21 a
120 kg/ha	132 b	204 b	81 b	0.66 b	1.02 a	0.44 a	37 a
80 kg/ha	61 a	119 a	76 a	1.36 c	2.38 b	1.52 b	52 b

^a Av of 4 replications. In a column under each planting method, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

and transplanting. Number of eggs was counted in a 1-m quadrat and expressed on a per area and per plant basis.

For both planting methods, eggs were most abundant by area on the more densely spaced plants (see table). *ℒ*

Effect of nitrogen and carbofuran on gall midge (GM) and white stem borer (SB) infestation in Nigeria

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In 1984 wet season we studied the effect of N fertilizer and granular carbofuran application on GM *Orseolia oryzivora*

Harris and Gagne and white SB *Maliarpha separatella* Ragonot infestation on rice plants at Badeggi, Nigeria. The site was on the irrigated lowland research farm of NCRI.

The field trial was in a split-plot randomized block design with three replications on an acid Oxisol (Agaie soil series). Three-week-old FARO 15 seedlings were planted in 15-m² plots at 20 × 2 km spacing. N as ammonium

sulfate was applied at 0, 50, 100, or 150 kg/ha as 50% basal and 25% each at active tillering and panicle initiation. Basal P and K were 40 kg/ha. Carbofuran granules (1.0 kg ai/ha) were applied at 1, 30, and 60 d after transplanting (DT); 1 and 30 DT; 30 and 60 DT. GM damage was measured at 70 DT as the number of onion shoots to total tillers in 50 hills/plot. SB damage was measured by dissecting

Effect of N and carbofuran on GM and SB infestation, Badeggi, Nigeria, 1984 wet season. ^a

Treatment	GM damage (% onion shoots)	SB-damaged stems (%)	Yield components and total yield		
			Tillers/hill	Panicles/hill	Yield (t/ha)
N level (kg/ha)					
0	4.2 a	35.3 a	7.3 b	6.8 b	2.59 a
50	4.6 a	36.4 ab	8.8 a	8.1 a	2.12 a
100	4.8 a	39.3 bc	9.5 a	8.7 a	2.13 a
150	1.2 b	40.1 c	9.8 a	8.7 a	2.82 a
Carbofuran application ^b (1.0 kg ai/ha)					
1	6.0 cd	39.7 b	9.3 a	8.4 a	2.19 a
30	4.7 abc	31.6 ab	8.1 a	7.5 a	2.71 a
60	5.6 bcd	38.3 ab	9.3 a	8.7 a	2.58 a
1 and 30	3.6 a	35.3 a	9.3 a	8.1 a	2.88 a
30 and 60	4.1 ab	34.5 a	8.6 a	7.7 a	2.83 a
Untreated	7.2 d	41.0 b	8.5 a	1.3 a	2.51 a

^a Separation of means in a column by DMRT at the 5% level. ^b Days after transplanting.

stems from 20 hills/plot at 10 d before harvest.

GM and SB damage increased with applied N, but the number of tillers/hill and panicles/hill did not increase significantly beyond 0 kg N/ha. Yield did not differ significantly at different N levels (see table).

Applying carbofuran significantly influenced GM and SB damage. Applying carbofuran at 1 and 30 DT significantly reduced GM damage. SB damage was significantly reduced with applications at 1 and 30 DT or 30 and 60 DT. There were no significant differences in yield components or total yield (see table). *ℒ*

Effect of insecticides and variety on stem borer (SB) incidence

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We studied the effect of some insecticides and varieties on SB incidence at Badeggi in 1983 wet season. The field trial was in a split-plot randomized block design with four replications. Twenty-one-day-old FARO 11 and FARO 13 seedlings were transplanted in 25-m² plots at 25- × 25-cm spacing. Insecticides were applied 10, 30, 50, and 70 d after transplanting (DT). Deadhearts due to *Diopsis*

thoracica infestation in each plot were recorded 40 DT. Bored stems from *Maliarpha separatella* infestation were assessed by dissecting 20 randomly selected hills from each plot at 10 d before harvest (see table).

Carbofuran controlled *D. thoracica* most effectively, followed by BHC and decamethrin. Number of bored stems did not significantly differ among insecticide treatments. Carbofuran-treated plots had significantly fewer borers per plant than other plots, and yield was significantly higher.

FARO 11 had more deadhearts than FARO 13, but the difference was insignificant. FARO 11 had significantly more borers per plant. *ℒ*

Influence of N fertilizer on the population development of brown planthopper (BPH)

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We studied BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* biotype 2 reactions to different levels of N fertilizer on selected rices. BPH reared on IR26 were tested on susceptible IR26; Utri Rajapan, tolerant with no antibiosis; Triveni, moderate tolerance and antibiosis; and IR60, high antibiosis.

The N solution was prepared by mixing 125 g of ammonium sulfate containing 20% N in 375 ml water. In each of 2 clay pots lined with polyethylene bags and containing 2.5 kg

Effect of insecticides and varieties on SB incidence, Badeggi, Nigeria, 1983 wet season.

Insecticide	Treatment		Deadhearts 40 DT (%)	Bored stems at harvest (%)	Borers (no/20 hills)	Grain yield (t/ha)
	Formulation	Rate (kg ai/ha)				
BHC	20 EC	2.00	9	22	32	3.3
Decamethrin	2.5 EC	0.50	9	20	29	3.3
Diazinon	60 EC	2.00	21	22	28	2.1
Isoprocarb	75 WP	1.33	13	21	20	2.6
Carbofuran	10G	1.00	4	19	13	3.9
Control			17	22	32	2.8
LSD (P=0.05)			10	ns	10	0.6
Variety						
FARO 13			10	19	19	3.3
FARO 11			14	23	33	2.9
LSD (P=0.05)			ns	2	6	ns
Interaction (P=0.05)			14	ns	ns	ns

1. BPH weight on selected varieties grown under different N fertilizer rates, IIRRI.